

**THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP**

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In the conditions of modern society, the rapid development of the small business sector in the digital economy can be the only source of real restructuring of society, ensuring the orientation of all the main participants in economic and social processes towards an objectively determined participation in the functioning. market mechanism. Thus, the article attempts to substantiate the impact of the digital economy on improving the efficiency of small and private businesses in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Digital economy Small and private business Innovation National economy.

Improving the digital economy, scientific research on the social, economic, political and legal foundations, new innovations in the national economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan play an important role in society and directly depend on the implementation of large-scale reforms carried out today in the republic. Currently, the share of the digital economy in GDP in Uzbekistan is 2.2%. At the same time, the average optimal indicator is considered to be 7-8%. For example, in the UK it is 12.4%, South Korea - 6.9%, Russia - 2.8%, Kazakhstan - 3.9%. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, studying on a scientific basis largely depends on the trends and opportunities for the development of the digital economy and, in particular, the degree of penetration of modern digital technologies into various sectors of the economy, this is especially true for small businesses. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his Address to the Oliy Majlis: "This year we must make a radical turn in the development of the digital economy. This year, the development of the program "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" is envisaged. The digital economy in Uzbekistan is aimed at increasing the potential of the domestic ICT market, digital transformation of public services, creating favorable conditions for the further development and development of new information technologies and software products, developing human capital and improving the system of training and retraining of personnel in the field of information technology [1, p. . 3]. Despite the pandemic, in this direction in Uzbekistan, the development of the digital sector of the national economy is raised to the state level, and the necessary measures are proposed. This includes the introduction of an electronic document management system, the development of electronic platforms and the improvement of the legal

framework, the creation of electronic commerce in the regions of the republic. At present, the digital economy, operating on information technology platforms, is developing rapidly. This requires the creation of new models of such platforms. It should be noted that developing countries, like Uzbekistan, face the problem of developing a digital economy, similar to the general problems they face. This is a weak telecommunications infrastructure and communication is one of the main problems today, and not only in Uzbekistan. Due to low investment in information and communication technologies (ICT), which is 2.8 percent of the total investment, the density of communication base stations in the country remains very low (one base station per 1,000 people). In contrast, in Kazakhstan, for example, one such station serves ICT consumption for 643 inhabitants, and in Russia for 235. All this leads to the fact that “bad” Internet and mobile services slow down the growth of digitalization and increase the digital divide. Compared to the CIS average in 2020, the average Internet speed (mobile and fixed broadband) in Uzbekistan was about half as fast. This had a very strong effect during the outbreak of the coronavirus, when a huge load fell on digital platforms. The lack of digital skills in Uzbekistan can become a serious obstacle to digital transformation in the republic, as one of the few developing countries with absolute adult literacy rates (100% in 2019) compared to the same level of GDP per capita [4. With. 12]. On the other hand, in developing countries, despite the high level of adult literacy, digital literacy remains at a low level. Perhaps this can be explained by the low level of ICT use in schools. Due to the weak digital infrastructure and the lack of digital skills in the country, digital trade is developing at a slow pace. The adopted “Program for the Development of the Digital Economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2035” sets the task: to form a system of support and incentive measures that motivate economic entities for digital innovations and research in the field of digital technologies [1. With. 2]. A tool or a way to increase and develop innovative entrepreneurship is the introduction of digital technologies in the work of small enterprises in the digital economy, which provides for increasing the competitiveness of small enterprises. This allows you to get the maximum profit, but only if you create high-tech goods and services that are in demand by society using digital technologies. As we all already know, entrepreneurial activity, today, is understood as its organization within the competence of the entrepreneur himself in the context of the development of the digital economy. Here it should be taken into account that entrepreneurial risk can increase dramatically when small enterprises use digital technologies. The use of production and financial

resources of small businesses based on digitalization can be both extensive and intensive. The extensive use of the digital economy and its development is focused on the involvement of additional resources in production. The intensification of increasing the efficiency of production of small enterprises consists, first of all, in the high-quality and efficient use of ICT so that the results of production grow faster than the costs of it, so that by involving relatively fewer resources in production, great results can be achieved. The basis of such intensive development is currently the digital economy. The analysis of production intensification requires the classification of factors of extensive and intensive development of digitalization. The incompetence of many current entrepreneurs, which is expressed in insufficient knowledge in such areas as management, marketing, finance, lack of sufficient experience in management, difficulties in solving non-standard tasks, certain skills in the effective and full use of information and communication technologies, leads to the fact that small business is developing at an insufficiently fast pace [3, p. eight]. In Uzbekistan, investments are needed in the development of human capital, and its relevance is increasing with the development of the digital economy. This is due not only to the release of new high-tech products, but also to insufficient funding for this process, which is one of the important factors in the problems of small business development [2, p. 13]. Thus, having made a small analysis of the ongoing processes in the republic in the direction of increasing the efficiency of small businesses in the digital economy, it must be said that the implementation of state programs for the development of digitalization provides for the adaptation of new technologies to business needs within the framework of public-private partnership. And it is necessary to start with changes in the process of obtaining education at all existing levels. Here it is necessary to expand the use of digital technologies, create appropriate conditions, change educational programs, in terms of the formation of new competencies of knowledge and skills demanded by the digital economy, which will further develop a favorable environment for creating a new type of competent entrepreneurs.

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